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When Pluriversal International Relations Meet Narratives About Confucius Institute in Finland

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Confucius Institutes (CIs) are among the most widely reported Chinese forms of soft power in both Chinese and Western media. The Chinese media tend to be overly sanguine, while the Western media tends to be overly critical. Between these discourses, a number of serious English-language academic publications written by Western or Chinese scholars present more balanced views (Repnikova 2022; Franceschini and Loubere 2022; Hubbert 2019; Hartig 2015). In 2025, Jinghan Zeng, a professor at City University of Hong Kong, released a memoir detailing his experiences as CI director at Lancaster University in the UK. This type of publication, based on personal experience, is relatively uncommon. Both Zeng's memoir and many English-language academic publications express similar concerns about the oversimplification of the complexities of CIs, cautioning against viewing them purely as a Chinese tool to exercise soft power and conduct all sorts of ill-intentioned influences overseas. However, journalists and the public rarely consult this literature. In the case of CIs, the Western media is far more influential than the academic research.

All of these publications and the generation of various narratives about CIs predated my appointment as one of the very few Taiwan-born foreign directors of a CI in January 2016, and they have continued since. My experiences and views largely concur with Zeng's and with most English-language academic literature. If there is anything new in this autobiographical article for the launching issue of *Pluriversal International Relations*, it lies in a critical reflection of my journey with CI and how, based on that experience, I recalibrated my thinking on how the Chinese manage their international cooperation.

While a small number of Taiwanese CI directors had worked for Western universities before me, to my knowledge, when I took up the CI directorship at the University of Helsinki (UH), Finland, in 2016, I was the only one without naturalized citizenship in another Western country. So I was, in that sense, a 'pure Taiwanese'. The CI at the university had existed before my arrival. However, in 2016, for the first time, UH decided to hire a full professor of Chinese studies who would at the same time serve as director of the Finnish CI to manage Chinese language teaching. I ran the CI for seven years, until January 2023, when UH decided not to extend its cooperation agreement with the Chinese side. Since then, UH has entrusted nondegree Mandarin teaching to its language centre, using its own resources.

Many have questioned how a 'pure Taiwanese' could run a CI? Members of the PRC diaspora in Finland, the Taiwanese diaspora, scholars, CI staff, Western journalists and presumably many at the then-Hanban headquarters in Beijing all raised an eyebrow at my appointment. Yet, the UH selection committee made the appointment independently, without Chinese intervention. (Certainly, if Beijing holds the power to make the decision, it is highly probable that I will not be selected.) Because bystanders (e.g., China experts in Finland) and stakeholders (e.g., Hanban, CI staff) had preconceived notions of what CI stands for and what a 'pure Taiwanese' scholar should be, my appointment became both a

surprise and a puzzle. A Taiwanese diplomat jokingly told me that the Finns had demonstrated great wisdom by applying the Chinese concept of using barbarians to control barbarians (以夷制夷) to run the CI, naming using an outsider like me to control another outsider, which was the CI in this case. Because my appointment was unprecedented, everyone followed the experimental journey to see how it would unfold.

Over those seven years, many events that Western China experts predicted would happen to me did occur, though in more creative ways than they had imagined. Many things that educated guesses suggested would not happen also occurred. For instance, no suppression of academic freedom or interference from Beijing or the Chinese embassy took place during my term. However, subtle warnings appeared, particularly when the Chinese side learned of the possible nonrenewal of the CI agreement. The warning was elegantly inscribed in calligraphy by the staff of the Chinese embassy and was personally handed to me. It featured four Chinese characters that translate to ‘breezes come to you (清風自來).’ The individual who presented the gift elaborated that the complete poem conveys the message: ‘If you take no action, breezes will come to you. If you take actions, breezes will still come to you.’ Therefore, the underlying suggestion is that I should refrain from attempting to influence the presence of CI in UH, as breezes will come to me regardless.

I met Chinese officials who gave me the cold shoulder but also others who, despite our differences, tried to befriend me and seek common ground for cooperation. Among the Chinese staff with whom I worked, I encountered all types of people with different personalities, backgrounds and expectations for their temporary jobs in Finland. I also learned that the Finnish directors before me had very different personalities, which sometimes encouraged productive cooperation and sometimes fermented distrust and conflict. In sum, expert presumptions are valid, but the individuals involved in the daily practice of CI cooperation create both predictable results and counterintuitive outcomes. My perspective aligns with the conclusions drawn in the research conducted by Polakiewicz and Seiwert (2025) regarding CIs in Germany.

A Finnish director would be less likely to receive a warning disguised in such a gift as the aforementioned calligraphy because it would be hard for a Finnish native speaker to decipher a Chinese poem unless the Chinese embassy staff believed that this person’s Chinese skill was advanced enough. Were the director representing the Finnish side a Mainland Chinese, he or she would most likely get the same kind of gift as well.

These experiences provided valuable insights for theorizing the implementation of Chinese cooperative initiatives, not just CIs but also the well-known Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) projects around the world (Chen 2024; Chen and Ristivojević 2023; Chen 2023; Chen 2022; Chen 2020a). The essence of my theory is that localisation of a cooperative project is a necessary process that involves not only local and Chinese actors but also, at times, transnational ones who negotiate how a project will be accepted, accommodated and implemented at the host-state level. The nitty-gritty of the evolution of each cooperative project requires serious ethnographic fieldwork to analyse empirically. Nevertheless, the theory is important because it guides researchers to see that treating any Chinese project merely as an influencing tool, as most Western journalistic writings do, is incorrect. The nuances of interaction and negotiation between Chinese and foreign partners matter. Equally important are the ways in which

individuals interpret cooperation and adjust their perspectives—and even identities—during the negotiation process.¹

It is true that CIs have largely lost their appeal in the liberal West; the UH, too, did not renew its cooperation. As I had already predicted, the irony is that China's ambitious plan of using CIs to promote its culture and Mandarin often conflicted with its top-down management style—often framed as a feature of authoritarianism—and with the different operational values of host countries. As all CIs are localised projects, no two are alike. However, a single CI accused of harbouring a potential spy will immediately cause a heated debate to erupt in local and international news and the CI brand to be tarnished (e.g., Galindo 2019; Januzi 2020). Eventually, the Chinese government disbanded Hanban and created new institutions to address these problems.² However, the fact that China itself disbanded Hanban ironically raised more questions than it answered for foreign cooperators about the motives behind such a dramatic reform. Conversations held anonymously with insiders lead me to surmise that the new institutions might be old wine presented in a new bottle.

The Chinese side, with its myriad actors trying to run the CI brand successfully amid setbacks, needs time to grow and mature. The foreign hosts of these projects also need time to learn about the cooperation and evaluate its worth. However, Western media operate on a fast and sensationalist logic. I learned that despite my efforts to inform journalists of the need to avoid oversimplifying CI matters, such remarks have never been published. Pluriversal approaches, as advocated by this new journal, are consistent with scholarly trends to decolonise many things in our imperfect world (Chen 2026). However, I pessimistically believe that this remains an intellectual exercise that might, with luck, influence policy only if its messages reach to the right people without unnecessary media intervention.

Conflict of interest statement

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

Research ethics statement

As this contrapuntal review does not involve the collection or analysis of empirical data, no research activities requiring ethics approval were undertaken.

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¹ For instance, I have conducted research on the evolution of the Polar Silk Road in Finland (Chen 2020b) and highlighted the significance of private entrepreneur Peter Vesterbacka in advocating for the necessity of the Polar branch of the BRI in Finland. Vesterbacka is recognised as one of Finland's prominent entrepreneurs. He co-founded the Angry Birds video game franchise and established Slush, an international initiative that organises startup-related events in Helsinki and various other countries, including China. However, the Finnish government has consistently refrained from endorsing the BRI, despite the efforts of private entrepreneurs to develop and negotiate a Polar branch of the BRI. The negotiation and adaptation of Vesterbacka's narratives have evolved over the years, but this aspect falls outside the scope of this article.

² In 2020, Hanban underwent a rebranding and is now known as the Centre for Language Education and Cooperation. Additionally, it established the Chinese International Education Foundation to oversee CIs and related initiatives.

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